

Social Work in Corrections Institutions and Re-Socialization of Convicted Women

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Abstract:- Humanity has been concerned with punishing lawbreakers for a very long time. The personality of the convicted person changes significantly while they are imprisoned and cut off from society. As a result, the personal values of women come to dominate their lives, giving them a seemingly non-social existence, while values that reflect their social nature become less important. Serving a sentence results in permanent losses for women, their families, communities, and society at large. Every woman possesses the capacity to become a mother both as a biological and social being and as an individual. Using Sierra Leone as an example, a sociological study found that in 2023, 10% of charges made by the police were for fraudulent conversation. Most women are deprived of their basic rights whilst incarcerated and others experienced abuse from fellow prisoners.

Keywords: Prison, Corrections, Women, Convict, Social Work, Conflict, Crime.

I. INTRODUCTION

The problem of punishing people who break the law has worried humanity for a long time. In conditions of imprisonment, in isolation from society, the personality of the convicted person changes significantly, as a result of which individual values acquire the greatest significance for him, providing a seemingly non-social existence, and values, reflecting the social essence of a person fade into the background. At the end of the sentence, the convict returns to society, the laws of which he must comply, but for several reasons not always able to follow them, since social adaptation is difficult for them. That is why the work of institutions performing criminal punishments, and the problem of re-socialization of convicts should be taken into consideration.

This situation makes it easier to address the issue of societal decriminalization. It is hard to successfully address this issue without social work connections between correctional facilities and the social work system at large [1, 6]. Depending on the type of crimes they committed, the level of public danger, their prior criminal history, and the various punitive measures available, different categories of convicts receive different treatment when it comes to the execution of their punishment and the application of corrective measures. As a result, their age, gender, and other psychological and pedagogical factors should all be considered while developing educational work with them.

First off, women who have been given prison sentences are also affected by what has been said. The phrase "condemned woman" involuntarily" cuts the ear."Since childhood, the words "woman" and "mother," "kindness," "tenderness," and "kindness" have been used interchangeably. Unfortunately, this expression is widely used in many nations in the third millennium. A person's life becomes challenging after conviction and confinement in locations of liberty restriction.

The term of serving a sentence carries irreversible losses for women, their micro-environment, family, and society as a whole. Every woman is a carrier of maternal potential as a biological and social unit, and also as a unique subject, and has gone through its path at all stages of development need-motivational sphere of motherhood [2, 4-5]. The problem of motherhood of convicted women is always acutely relevant - after all, behind the woman lies the fate of her young child. This category of women often has a desire to give up their children, while they are often alienated and quite aggressive.

II. DISCUSSIONS

According to the findings of a sociological study that used Sierra Leone as an example in 2023, 10% of charges brought by the police were for fraudulent conversion. The misuse of property for reasons other than those for which it was given or intended is the subject of the offense.[10]. There is little distinction between the criminal and civil components of the crime of fraudulent conversion, and some aspects of it veer toward debt default. Charges are frequently brought when the debtor is simply unable to pay back financial obligations, even though the explicit intent to defraud is not always obvious.[11]. In Sierra Leone, women frequently engage in informal trading as a type of economic activity. As dealers, they frequently borrow money in this manner through microfinance organizations. These traders tend to be illiterate and mathematically challenged, and disagreements over payments and obligations are frequent. Another worrying tendency is the detention of women despite there being no proof that they are their husbands' accomplices or acting in their place.

Gender inequality and female poverty are persistent issues in Sierra Leone that have a direct influence on women who are being held in pretrial custody. The 'feminization of poverty' has been referred to as a phenomenon where there are allegedly considerable gender disparities[13]. The bail

system in Sierra Leone has been dubbed "rigorous," "inconsistent," and "excessive"[14]. A typical bail condition calls for the production of two sureties, each of whom must show title deeds as proof of property ownership and who must live in the same city as the court [15]. Women have not traditionally been allowed to own property, and poor female inmates are unlikely to have close male friends who own land.

In the case of women serving sentences, the situation is extremely complicated: they stand out from the series of "just a woman", and "mother-woman" The past dominates them, where the stages of their personal development and, in particular, the stages of development of the need-motivational sphere of motherhood. At the last stage of this path: the "mother-child" - the woman is already alienated by society, and she demonstrates and experiences alienation from other people, from the world, and sometimes from herself.

A woman's alienation can extend to her child in a state of damaged, alienated motherhood, a woman needs social and psychological support together with her child [4, p.63]. Comparative analysis of social research data indicates negative trends: an increase in the number of convicted women without families, prospects worsening due to age creation of families, high rates of family breakdown due to increased time of imprisonment, and deterioration of health. Each of the selected groups requires a special approach when organizing work on the preservation, creation, and restoration of family relationships and social useful connections. Prospects for a successful resolution of the family. The problems of convicted women are directly related to their age. The majority of convicted women are in one of the most socially productive ages - from 25 to 39 years.

Psychological studies of convicted women have shown that in their mass they do not have qualities that could significantly complicate the prevention of crimes on their part, the process of their corrections, and re-education. Compared to male criminals they are less likely to have asocial attitudes, and they lack persistent criminal convictions; socio-political adaptation, although broken, has no serious defects, except professional criminals and persons socially maladjusted due to with "homelessness", alcoholism, drug addiction, and various mental abnormalities and disorders [5, 73].

Objectively unfavorable for effective re-socialization of women are the conditions of detention in the correctional facility: lack of normal living conditions, problems of compliance with hygiene requirements, poor nutrition, lack of individual space, strict regulation of life routine, limitation of opportunities for manifestation independence and responsibility, narrowing the scope of social contacts and alienation. They practically do not implement such forms of maintaining family and social contacts, such as short-term trips and vacations with departure from the correctional institution. The system needs to be corrected by their social interaction with family and healthy forces in

society. Characteristics of methods of social work in general, and social working with convicts in particular is very difficult, an insufficiently developed but relevant problem of theory and practice new for the penitentiary system, referral to professional activities.

Methods of activity of a social worker in the penitentiary sphere are built, first of all, according to a plan for the consistent elimination of all objective negative phenomena of socio-economic, socio-psychological nature, eradication of negative circumstances in the organization of life, activities, everyday life and leisure of specific people [6, p. 118]. In general, the activities of a social worker in a penitentiary system is possible in the following directions:

- Providing psychological assistance in the traditional sense – diagnostic consultation and preventive measures.
- Improving the psychological state of convicts to destructive conflicts and negative perceptions of correctional influences.
- Conducting corrective psychological correction convicted in Art. 61 UN Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners indicate the functions of a social worker in correctional institutions:
 - support and strengthening of socially useful ties with family;
 - Support and strengthen socially useful connections with social (public) organizations;
 - Protection of civil interests of convicted persons;
 - Protection of the rights of convicted persons to social security and others social benefits.

At the main stage of serving a sentence, specialists in social work predict options for the development of a difficult life situation convicted person, plan and draw up a program for her correction and re-socialization. At the same time, taking into account their socio-psychological characteristics need to focus on eliminating and preventing social problems; and positive personal development through creating conditions for realizing positive potential, self-affirmation, and implementation in socially significant activities (production work, training, creativity, improvement of life, leisure, organizing charity, helping those in need, including - children kept in orphanages, boarding schools, orphanages); creation favorable emotional background in communication; assistance in obtaining social benefits; involvement in the planning and implementation process plan of the squad leader, psychologist, social work specialist, and also the convicted person, her relatives, adult children.

Conducting conversations with convicted women is of great importance on topics that concern them. It is a conversation that makes it possible to learn a better person, it is at the same time a way of providing social and psychological impact. While talking about herself and her life Convict puts her thoughts in order and often reveals herself Some cause-and-effect dependencies make constructive conclusions, and all this can happen both during the conversation itself and after her. The conversation should always be based on the personality characteristics of female criminals, the reason for it, the time

and place carried out, and the situation that develops in its course. The main goal of this kind of conversation is to help a woman who has committed a crime, by solving vital problems for her. It is expedient to organize in a correctional institution, within the framework of ongoing social work, and cultural work (amateur performances, folk theater, performance of various products characteristic of folk crafts, technical creativity organization of exhibitions of crafts, circle work) [7].

Activities among convicts, assistance in the development of hobbies, and activities favorite thing within the limits of the possible and reasonable in correctional institutions [8]. An important direction in social work with convict women is the provision of medical and social assistance and the organization of compulsory treatment of those who have general or chronic diseases. Organization of work with women with socially significant diseases (tuberculosis, alcoholism, drug addiction, mental disorders, sexually transmitted diseases, AIDS) is carried out by specialists in the constituent entities of the Russian Federation by current legislation aimed at ensuring the rights of citizens in receiving medical care. Providing useful employment is not an unimportant factor in the process of adaptation of convicts to life at large and carrying out social work in general. Involvement by specialists sentenced to study, obtain basic general education and prison-wide vocational training will allow women to get paid work after liberation.

There are vocational schools in women's colonies or their branches, where convicts are trained in sewing skills production (seamstress, service technician, electrician, etc.). To provide individual influence on convicted women, and to mobilize their resources to get out of difficult life situations, social work specialists attract members board of trustees or council of relatives. They also use opportunities for public organizations to involve convicted women in activities related to assisting individuals to convicted women who need it. Social work is at the final stage of serving a sentence aimed at preparing women for liberation. Convicts, those preparing for life in freedom need some help. She carried out classes at the School in preparation for liberation.

In Sierra Leone, since the institution transformed into Correctional Service in the year 2014, it was only in 2019, that the Sierra Leone Correctional Services constructed a makeshift child-friendly structure, in the female Correctional Centre to keep up with international best practices with regards children in prisons with their mothers, as is stipulated in No. 28 of the Mandela Rules: "In women's Prisons, there shall be a special accommodation for all necessary prenatal and post-natal care and treatment...

If a child is born in prison, this fact shall not be mentioned in the birth certificate", and No 58 (1) of the Bangkok Rules: "The environment provided for such children's upbringing shall be as close as possible to that of a child outside prison."

Since the opening of the child-friendly center, a lot of organizations and individuals have made donations of toys and learning materials for the kids."Kids like to play and watch cartoon movies. Social Workers in Sierra Leone realized how important it was for children to be cared for, noting the kids were not the ones who committed the crimes, so they deserve uplifting treatment from their mothers; the kid's diet is also different from their mothers'[16].

III. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it should be noted that social work in the penitentiary system as a branch of scientific knowledge, educational program, and direction of practical activities of correctional institutions are at the stage of formation and formation. Today there is a need to form its organizational model, clarify its content, and optimize technologies for providing assistance, support, and protection of convicts. It also seems appropriate to integrate social work in the penitentiary system into state and general social systems for providing the population, especially its most vulnerable layers [9].

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